

Newsletter

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February 8, 2023

We kicked off 2023 with great news: the launch version of our Circular Potential Information Platform - [#CPIM](#) !

In this newsletter, you will find the summary of our [#ReincarnaTECH](#) series dedicated to explaining our [#CPIM](#) and an invitation to discover it virtually.

What is the CP-IM Platform?

The overall objective of the Reincarnate project is to create technical, commercial and social instruments within the real estate and construction sector which will **enable the extension of the lifetime of building products, elements and materials and foster their reuse** in other projects and settings.

CP-IM, the Circular Potential Information Platform, is the essential segment of the Reincarnate project whose function is to provide the centralization of all necessary information and data needed for the evaluation of elements at all systemic levels of a building for the avoidance of construction waste and the best reuse of it.

Avoiding and reusing construction waste

While #CPIM will be created as dynamic integration of several distinct components, the launch version consists of the integration of its two core components: the DMO RE Suite real estate information management platform and the Mainflux open-source IoT Platform. The following article summarises this launch version: <https://www.reincarnate-project.eu/reincarnatech-1-0-the-circular-potential-information-platform-cp-im-by-reincarnate/>

The Real Estate Suite (RE Suite) application: collecting, structuring, analysing and disclosing information

RE Suite is one of the main CP-IM Platform applications and a core element. The RE Suite (short for Real Estate Suite) is a real estate information management platform. It assists real estate owners, managers and users with and through collecting, structuring, analysing and disclosing information. The following article presents the RE Suite application, its function and usability within the #CPIM:

[//www.reincarnate-project.eu/reincarnatech-2-0-the-real-estate-suite-re-suite-application/](https://www.reincarnate-project.eu/reincarnatech-2-0-the-real-estate-suite-re-suite-application/)

The Mainflux open-source IoT Platform: providing real-time data communication pipelines from physical data sources

The Mainflux open-source IoT Platform is one of the core components of the launch version. Mainflux is an open-source IoT platform (Apache 2.0 licence) with complete full-scale capabilities for developing IoT solutions, IoT applications and smart connected products. The following article explains the Mainflux open-source IoT Platform and its operation within #CPIM in this phase of the project: <https://www.reincarnate-project.eu/reincarnatech-3-0-the-mainflux-iot-platform-2/>

The launch version of the CP-IM platform: a major milestone

RE Suite and Mainflux components have distinct roles in the platform. Users interact with the Mainflux platform for 'thing' and 'channel' management, managing their population of sensors and actuators. Users interact with the RE Suite for various workflows: portfolio management, condition assessment and circular potential analysis. The following article illustrates the architecture and what is coming up next: <https://www.reincarnate-project.eu/reincarnatech-4-0-the-launch-version-reincarnate-cpim-platform/>

This Friday, we will host a live demo of the platform. Follow our workshop live-tweeting session and discover the [#CPIM](https://twitter.com/ReincarnateEU) ... <https://twitter.com/ReincarnateEU>

By subscribing to our newsletter, you will receive the demo video and discover how out CP-IM works!

[I want to watch the video demo!](#)

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🤖 Are you interested in our Circular Potential Information Platform - [#CPIM](#) ? Do you want to see how it performs?

Read our [#ReincarnateNews](#) on this first milestone achieved, comprising a summary of the [#ReincarnaTECH](#) series explaining with all the details the launch version of our platform with its components, functions and more.

📺 Get ready to watch it in action!

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